

THE PATHOGENESIS OF DEFICIENCY DISEASE.

No. IV. THE INFLUENCE OF A SCORBUTIC DIET ON THE ADRENAL GLANDS.

BY

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THE influence of a scorbutic diet of crushed oats and autoclaved milk on the adrenal glands was studied in guinea-pigs.

The animals were isolated in separate cages. The experiment was continued until death occurred. Autopsies were performed with the attention to detail previously described.⁽¹⁾ Aërobic cultures of the heart's blood at autopsy gave negative results in four cases, positive results in one (No. 5, Table 1). In this case the organism isolated failed to kill guinea-pigs on subcutaneous injection, in large dosage.

MORBID ANATOMY.

Increase in size of the adrenal glands together with greater or lesser degrees of congestion were the main naked-eye changes observed. The yellow colour of the organs was usually found to have given place to a reddish-yellow tinge. The superficial vessels presented varying degrees of engorgement. Minute hæmorrhagic effusions under the serous coat were frequently encountered.

The weight of the adrenals of guinea-pigs dying in consequence of the scorbutic diet was approximately double that of health (Table I). Whereas the gross weight of both organs in healthy guinea-pigs ranged between 0.390 and 0.520, with an average weight of 0.467 grams, in

guinea-pigs fed on the scorbutic dietary the weight of both glands ranged between 0.850 and 1.150 grams, with an average weight of 0.955 grams. The increase in weight due to the scorbutic diet was even more marked when the weight of the glands was calculated per kilo of *original* and of *final* body-weight (Chart I).

CHART I.

Char I. Showing weight of adrenals and total adrenalin per kilo of original (OB-W) and of final (FB-W) body-weight, also total adrenalin per gram of gland in (α) healthy guinea-pigs (black columns) and in (β) guinea-pigs fed on a scorbutic diet (shaded columns).

ADRENALIN-CONTENT OF THE ENLARGED GLANDS.

The adrenalin-content was estimated by the method of Folin, Cannon and Dennis.⁽³⁾ In each case one gland was used for adrenalin-

estimation, the other for histological study. On the presumption that both organs were affected in like degree, the total adrenalin-content of both adrenals was calculated from the results obtained with one gland. In some instances the right gland was used for adrenalin-estimation, in others the left. The results of these estimations are shown in the following table (Table I), and are illustrated graphically in Chart I.

TABLE I.

Showing the adrenalin-content of the adrenal glands, the total adrenalin per kilo of body-weight, etc., in (a) five guinea-pigs fed on a scorbutic diet, and (b) in four healthy guinea-pigs fed on normal food.

Number of guinea-pig.	Original weight of guinea-pig in grams.	Final weight of guinea-pig in grams.	Weight of adrenals in grams.	Weight of adrenals per kilo of original body-weight in grams.	Weight of adrenals per kilo of final body-weight in grams.	Total adrenalin in both adrenal glands in grams.	Total adrenalin per kilo of original body-weight in grams.	Total adrenalin per kilo of final body-weight in grams.	Total adrenalin per gram of gland.	Experimental or control animal.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1	550	390	·850	1·545	2·179	·000113	·000205	·000289	·000132	Experimental. Do. Do. Do. Do.
2	520	400	1·029	1·978	2·572	·000143	·000275	·000357	·000139	
3	500	320	·850	1·700	2·656	·000096	·000192	·000300	·000112	
4	550	320	·900	1·636	2·812	·000116	·000210	·000362	·000128	
5	520	390	1·150	2·211	2·948	·000086	·000165	·000220	·000074	
	528	364	·955	1·814	2·633	·000110	·000209	·000305	·000117	Averages.
7	570	620	·390	·684	·629	·000253	·000443	·000408	·000648	Control. Do. Do. Do.
8	610	610	·520	·852	·852	·000216	·000354	·000354	·000415	
9	610	610	·460	·754	·754	·000253	·000414	·000414	·000550	
10	670	670	·500	·746	·746	·000233	·000347	·000347	·000466	
	615	627	·467	·759	·745	·000238	·000389	·000380	·000519	Averages.

NOTE :—I am indebted to Colonel Cornwall, I.M.S., for the figures relating to guinea-pigs Nos. 8, 9 and 10. Owing to difficulty in obtaining supplies of pure anhydrous phosphoric acid and of sodium-tungstate I was unable to estimate the adrenalin-content of the adrenal glands in my controls to this experiment (with the exception of Pig No. 7). The figures given for cases Nos. 8, 9 and 10 are the results of estimations made by Colonel Cornwall for another purpose in three healthy guinea-pigs from laboratory stock.

ANALYSIS OF TABLE I.

(1) The total quantity of adrenalin in both glands in guinea-pigs fed on a scorbutic diet was less than half that present in healthy guinea-pigs (Table I, col. 7) although the weight of the organs was more than twice as great in the former as in the latter. (Table I, cols. 4, 5, 6.)

(2) Similarly the total adrenalin per kilo of *original* body-weight (*i.e.*, the weight of the animal before the experiment commenced) was little more than half that of health. (Table I, col. 8.)

(3) When calculated against the *final* body-weight (Table I, col. 9) of the guinea-pig, the total adrenalin per kilo was found to be less markedly reduced; that is to say, the total adrenalin-production does not diminish in proportion to the diminution of body-weight.

(4) The total adrenalin per gram of gland was less than one-fourth of that found in health. (Table I, col. 10.)

(5) It will be noted that in guinea-pig No. 5, in which a coliform organism was cultured from the heart's blood at autopsy, the adrenalin-content was considerably less than in the other four animals in which no infection was detected by aërobic methods of culture.

A pronounced reduction in the amount of adrenalin in the suprarenal glands was thus found to result in guinea-pigs from a scorbutic dietary of crushed oats and autoclaved milk.

In connexion with these findings it is of interest to direct attention to the fact that the total adrenalin per gram of gland in healthy pigeons is ten times greater (.0023 grams) than in healthy guinea-pigs (.00023 grams). This greater proportion of adrenalin in birds may bear some relationship to the fact that they excrete uric acid as such. The work of Bauer,⁽⁵⁾ which leads him to believe that 'the function of the adrenal cortex is the making of pigment from the superfluous uric acid in the blood,' is of interest in this connexion. He considers that the pigment, which he believes to be made by the cortex, is transformed by the medulla into adrenalin.

A further point of interest in connexion with these findings is the contrast they afford to the great increase in the adrenalin-content of the adrenal glands which occurs in pigeons wholly deprived of accessory food factors of all classes. In another place⁽⁴⁾, I have shown that the adrenalin-content of these organs in birds is largely dependent on the class of accessory food factor which is absent from the dietary.

HISTO-PATHOLOGY.

The histological changes in the adrenal glands which result from a scorbutic dietary comprise :—

- (1) Hæmorrhagic infiltration, and
- (2) Degenerative changes in the cellular elements of the medulla and cortex.

Hæmorrhagic infiltration.—There are two features of importance in connexion with the hæmorrhagic infiltrations :—

- (1) Their circumscribed character and situation in the adrenal cortex ; and
- (2) the fact that they may occur before any *clinical* evidences of scurvy are observed, and even before any notable scorbutic changes are to be found at autopsy between cartilage and rib.

The circumscribed character of the hæmorrhagic infiltrations and their situation in the adrenal cortex are shown in Fig. 1. A higher magnification of a similar section is shown in Fig. 3. Through the kindness of Colonel Cornwall, I.M.S., I am enabled to show photomicrographs of sections of the adrenal from a case of street-virus rabies in a guinea-pig. These (Figs. 8 and 9) illustrate the radiating distribution of the capillary spaces of the adrenal cortex in guinea-pigs. They provide also an instructive contrast to the sections of adrenals from guinea-pigs fed on a scorbutic diet. It will be noted that in the latter the congestive process is not confined to engorgement of the capillary spaces of the cortex but results in more or less circumscribed hæmorrhagic infiltration of scattered areas of the cortex. These hæmorrhagic areas are of varying sizes ; their more or less uniform distribution around the periphery of the cortex is their characteristic feature. I have not observed this curious distribution of hæmorrhages in the adrenal glands of guinea-pigs dying of infectious diseases in which both cortex and medulla are often extensively congested. The hæmorrhagic areas were distributed more or less uniformly around the periphery of the cortex in three cases in the present series (Figs. 1 and 3). They were present on only one side of the adrenal cortex in one case. In the fifth case (Fig. 5) they were absent, a moderate degree of generalized hæmorrhagic infiltration of the cortex alone being present.

The changes in the cortical cells consist in (a) loss of their tessellated appearance, (b) vacuolation and disintegration of cells, and

PLATE XI.

FIG. 1. Photograph of section of adrenal gland from a guinea-pig fed on a scorbutic diet of crushed oats and autoclaved milk. Note: fourteen circumscribed areas of hæmorrhage distributed throughout the cortex. Some of these are indicated by the letter 'H'; the others are unmarked. The photograph was taken by interposing a lens ($\times 15$) between the bellows of the camera and the object. The magnification is roughly 20 to 30 diameters.

Fig. 1.

PLATE XII.

- Fig. 2. Section of adrenal gland of healthy guinea-pig, $\times 55$. Note : normal appearance of healthy cortex (C) and medulla (M).
- „ 3. Section of adrenal gland of guinea-pig which died in consequence of a scorbutic diet of crushed oats and autoclaved milk, $\times 55$. Note : circumscribed areas of hæmorrhage (H), disintegration of cellular elements of cortex (C), and of medulla (M). Compare with Fig. 1.

PLATE XII.

Fig. 2.

Fig. 3.

- FIG. 4.** Portion of adrenal cortex from a healthy guinea-pig, $\times 105$. Note: tessellated appearance of cortical cells and their darkly staining nuclei.
- „ **5.** Portion of adrenal cortex from a guinea-pig (No. 5, *vide* Table I) dying of experimentally produced scurvy, $\times 105$. Note: disappearance of tessellated structure, vacuolation of cortex (V), disappearance of nuclei and diffuse hæmorrhagic infiltration of cortex, also engorgement of cortical capillary spaces (C.E.).

Fig. 4.

Fig. 5.

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- FIG. 6. Portion of adrenal cortex from a guinea-pig (No. 2, *vide* Table I), dying in consequence of a scorbutic diet of crushed oats and autoclaved milk, $\times 105$. This animal showed prior to its death none of the clinical evidences of scurvy, although at autopsy it presented numerous hæmorrhages into the tissues. Note: loss of tessellated structure, marked vacuolation of cells, disappearance of nuclei, pronounced hæmorrhagic infiltration (H).
- „ 7. Shows the same appearances as in Figs. 5 and 6, but in more pronounced degree, $\times 105$. From guinea-pig No. 3, Table I.

PLATE XIV.

Fig. 6.

Fig. 7.

- FIG. 8. Section of adrenal gland from a guinea-pig dying of street-virus rabies (subdural inoculation), $\times 55$. Note: linear distribution of congestion (C), due to great engorgement of the radiating capillary spaces of the cortex. The distribution of the congestion is in marked contrast to that found to result from a scorbutic diet. Compare Figs. 1 and 2. (From a specimen kindly provided by Colonel Cornwall, I.M.S.)
9. A higher magnification of the adrenal cortex of a guinea-pig dying of street-virus rabies, $\times 105$. From the same section as in Fig. 8. Note: great engorgement of the cortical capillary spaces, little or no hæmorrhagic infiltration of cortex outside the capillary spaces, vacuolation of cortical cells, disappearance of nuclei. Compare with Figs. 5, 6 and 7.

Fig. 8.

Fig. 9.

(c) disappearance or loss of staining reactions of their nuclei. These changes are well seen in the photomicrographs which illustrate three different cases; they call for no further description.

The medulla is much disorganized and shows cellular disintegration with scattered blood cells lying throughout its substance. Usually it is possible to detect in healthy glands the chrome-staining granules of the medullary cells. In the case of guinea-pigs fed on the scorbutic dietary these granules are few or altogether wanting.

I have been much impressed with the fact that the histo-pathological changes I have described were present in the adrenals of guinea-pigs, fed on the scorbutic dietary, which exhibited during life no clinical evidences of scurvy. Depression of adrenal function may, therefore, be regarded as a pre-scorbutic manifestation of a dietary deficient in accessory food factors of the 'C' class.

SUMMARY.

A scorbutic diet gives rise in guinea-pigs to—

- (1) an increase in size and in weight of the adrenal glands;
- (2) a marked diminution in the adrenalin-content of these organs;
- (3) hæmorrhagic infiltration of the adrenal glands, usually circumscribed in extent and situated around the periphery of the adrenal cortex; and to
- (4) degenerative changes in the cellular elements of the adrenal cortex and medulla.

CONCLUSIONS.

1. A scorbutic diet causes pronounced depreciation in functional capacity of the adrenal glands in guinea-pigs.
2. The impairment of adrenal function occurs before clinical evidences of scurvy manifest themselves.

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